

MOIRÉ INTERFEROMETRY STRAIN ANALYSIS USING FFT TECHNIQUE FOR FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH HOLE

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the experimental technique of moiré interferometry, which produces fringe patterns displaying two-dimensional displacement fields, as applied to unidirectional graphite fiber reinforced composite laminates containing a small hole is first outlined. The fundamental principle using fast Fourier transform(FFT) method to evaluate the available interferograms of specimens is introduced, and based on which, a computer image processing system is then developed. With the application of present approach, an example of two-dimensional strain distribution near the hole area of the composite specimen is illustrated. The experimental result is compared with the prediction from finite element method.

Keywords: Moiré interferometry, composite laminate, fast-Fourier-transform(FFT).

1. Introduction

The behavior of fiber reinforced composite laminates with stress concentrations such as cutouts is of great interest in design because of the resulting significant variations of strength reduction and the damage growth around these stress concentrations in service. In order to employ composites in practice with confidence, it is necessary to evaluate their tolerance to flaws and stress concentrations. A typical problem in investigating the failure of laminated composite materials is the prediction of the direction of crack growth in the notched specimens. The study of unidirectional laminates represents a simpler and perhaps a fundamental investigation which should be understood completely before attempt is made to understand crack growth in laminates. The latter problem is inherently more complex since generally a three dimensional stress state exists in a notched multilayer laminate. It is important that a great deal of experimental and analytical work should be conducted to evaluate the behavior of composite laminates before the failure mechanics method can be applied. Stress and strain distributions in composite plates around stress concentration can be treated analytically using linear anisotropic elasticity and finite element methods. Some experimental methods have proven very powerful in verifying theoretical solutions in the linear range and supplementing them in the nonlinear range. Experimental approaches are especially useful in studying failure modes and analyzing the effects of damage in composites.

This investigation is concerned with the analysis of deformation response of the unidirectional composite laminate containing a circular hole. An experimental technique, Moiré interferometry, will be introduced to observe the behavior of unidirectional composite laminates with hole under off-axis tensile loading. The fast Fourier transform technique will be employed to process the moiré fringe patterns in order to obtain the strain distribution of the specimen. The predicted results from the finite element method will be compared with the experimental ones.

2. Experimental Procedure

Moiré interferometry is a nondestructive testing method, which combines the concepts and techniques of geometrical moiré and optical interferometry, for in-plane displacement field contouring of opaque flat surfaces. It extends the sensitivity of moiré method into the subwavelength range of visible light, capable of resolving very small displacements and suitable for the analysis of localized zones of very high strain gradients associated with material discontinuities of structural composites. The technique is characterized by a remarkable set of qualities: it is a real-time method and provides full-field displacement components with high sensitivity, i.e., information about all points in the area can be recorded and observed simultaneously, excellent fringe contrast, high spatial resolution and extensive range. A brief description of the moiré interferometry is presented below. More detailed discussions can be found in Ref[1].

In moiré interferometry, a high-frequency reflective phase grating is first applied onto the specimen surface and will hence deform together with the underlying specimen. A plane mirror is positioned perpendicular to this specimen grating and they are illuminated by a collimated beam of coherent, monochromatic laser light. A portion of the laser light beam strikes the specimen at angle $-\alpha$, while the other portion of the same beam is redirected by the plane mirror to arrive at the specimen with the symmetrical angle $+\alpha$. The relationship between this angle α , the laser light wavelength λ , and the initial frequency of the specimen grating f_s is

$$\sin \alpha = \lambda f_s \quad (1)$$

The two incident beams generate an interference pattern which functions as a virtual reference grating superimposed on the specimen grating plane. Its frequency is twice that of the specimen grating. The specimen grating and virtual reference grating interact to form a two-beam-interference moiré pattern. This is photographed by the camera, which is focused on the plane of the specimen. After loads are applied to the specimen, the moiré fringe pattern observed in the camera is a contour map in which the fringes, as in the case of classic moiré, are contours of constant displacement component and consecutive fringes differ by an amount equal to the spacing between lines on the virtual reference grating. Fringe order at any point is proportional to the in-plane displacement component at that point.

For this investigation, unidirectional composite laminates with a central hole made of 648 epoxy matrix reinforced by 65 percent volume of T300 graphite fibers subject to uniaxial tension as shown in Figure 1 will be examined in detail. The results for the laminate specimens with fiber orientation angles between the loading direction and principal direction of 0, 45, and 90 degrees are considered here. A phase-type cross-line grating of 1200 lines/mm is replicated on the specimen in order to simultaneously obtain both in-plane displacement components U and V, along x and y direction respectively. A moiré interferometry device schematically illustrated in Figure 2 is designed and constructed so as to allow measurement of both components of in-plane displacement field on the specimen surface. A 135 mW He-Ne laser LB provides a monochromatic and coherent light. The laser beam is reflected by mirrors M1 and M2 into a spatial filter SF. The spatial filter contains a microscope objective which focuses the laser light

at a point and diverges it beyond that point. A pinhole is positioned at the focal point in order to strip off light originating from the nonuniform exterior of the laser beam. The diverging beam of light is reflected by a parabolic mirror PM, the collimating element, to the specimen and mirrors MA, MC and MB. The light coming from the collimator is a beam of collimated, coherent, and monochromatic light. The light illuminates the mirror surface MB and the specimen, which is used to obtain the transverse moiré pattern. The two 45 degree mirrors MA and MC are adjusted to direct portions of the collimated beam at angles $+\alpha$ and $-\alpha$ in the vertical plane, to form the longitudinal moiré pattern. The viewing light from the specimen S encounters a beam splitter BS which divides the beam into two essentially equal parts. One part of the beam passes through the BS and the camera lens CL to a video camera VC. Another part of light emerging from the BS, the beam reflected by the BS, goes to a photographic camera CA. These cameras are used to capture the moiré fringe patterns for subsequent image processing. In present analysis, the video camera is used to record the moiré image of local zone near the hole area with great enlargement, while the photographic camera is employed to capture the global moiré fringe pattern of the specimen. As the arrangement presented is quite sensitive, all of the optical elements and the specially designed displacement screw-loading frame connected with a load cell are firmly mounted on a stiff and massive metal table which is supported by several inflatable air tyres in order to minimize vibration problems.

When employing the apparatus described above, the two in-plane displacement fields are examined independently. To obtain the V field on the camera screens, a sheet of opaque cardboard is inserted in front of the PM to block portion B of the incident collimated beam of light that provides the transverse moiré pattern. The U field appears when the card is placed on the PM such that portions A and C are blocked. The actual procedure for the moiré interferometry test is simple: (1) install the specimen in the loading fixture; (2) adjust the mirrors MA, MC, and MB for initial displacement U and V fields and capture them as reference states; (3) apply loads to the specimen and photograph the U and V fields.

3. Image Processing System-FFT Technique

As moiré interferometry provides abundant high-sensitive experimental information in the form of contour maps of displacement fields, to interpret accurately these fringe patterns is important prerequisite for the further response analysis of composite structures. The fast Fourier transform(FFT) technique, a widely used signal-processing and analysis concept^[2,3], will be employed in this study.

Generally, the light intensity function $i(x,y)$ of a fringe pattern can be expressed in the form

$$i(x,y) = a(x,y) + c(x,y) + c^*(x,y) \quad (2)$$

where $c(x,y)=b(x,y)\exp[j\phi(x,y)]$, j is the imaginary unit and $*$ denotes a complex conjugate, $a(x,y)$ and $b(x,y)$ represent irradiance variations arising from imperfect optic elements, and the interference phase $\phi(x,y)$ contains the desired information about specimen displacement.

As an example, consider a V-field fringe pattern. To obtain $\phi(x,y)$ separately from the unwanted $a(x,y)$ and $b(x,y)$, a FFT algorithm is utilized to compute the 1-D Fourier transform of Equation (2) for the variable y , with x being fixed as x_0 :

$$I(x_0, f) = A(x_0, f) + C(x_0, f) + C^*(x_0, f) \quad (3)$$

where $I(x_0, f)$, $A(x_0, f)$, and $C(x_0, f)$ are the 1-D Fourier spectra of $i(x_0, y)$, $a(x_0, y)$ and $c(x_0, y)$ respectively, and f is the spatial frequency in the y direction. Since the spatial variation of $a(x,y)$ is slow compared with the fringe spacing, the amplitude spectrum $A(x_0, f)$ will be a trimodal

function centered around the origin, while $C(x_o, f)$ and $C^*(x_o, f)$ are positioned symmetrically about the origin. $A(x_o, f)$ and $C^*(x_o, f)$ are filtered out by applying a bandpass-filter in the spatial frequency domain and the remaining spectrum which is not symmetrical and thus no longer corresponds to a real function in the spatial domain. Therefore, after inverse-Fourier-transformation of $C(x_o, f)$, $c(x_o, y)$ has a nonzero imaginary part. Thus, the interference phase $\phi(x_o, y)$ can be evaluated by

$$\phi(x_o, y) = \tan^{-1} \frac{\text{Im}[c(x_o, y)]}{\text{Re}[c(x_o, y)]} \quad (4)$$

The displacement V and strain ϵ_{yy} along the line x_o can be calculated as

$$V(x_o, y) = \frac{\phi(x_o, y)}{4\pi f_s}, \quad \text{and} \quad \epsilon_{yy}(x_o, y) = \frac{dV(x_o, y)}{dy} \quad (5)$$

Repeating the procedure above for different x_o values gives the strain distribution $\epsilon_{yy}(x, y)$ on the composite specimen.

4. Results and Discussions

Figure 3 shows moiré patterns representing contours of the displacement components along the x and y directions for the unidirectional composite laminate whose principal fiber direction coincides with the load direction (i.e., the 0° specimen). The patterns (a) and (b) are the V -field and U -field fringes respectively when the far-field extension strain is about $1310\mu\epsilon$. The patterns (c) and (d) correspond to the displacement fringes in y and x directions, respectively, at the strain level $1780\mu\epsilon$ distant to hole. Figure 4 represents the moiré patterns for 45° specimen. In Figure 4, (a) and (b) pictures are V and U patterns for the load of 440N , while (c) and (d) are the fringes under 1364N . Figure 5 displays the V and U deformation patterns for the 90° specimen. The load level for (a) and (b), V - and U -displacement fields, respectively, is 440N , while (c) and (d) are the fringe patterns corresponding to y and x directions for the load of 792N . Abrupt change in the moiré fringe pattern near the hole edge, which represents a macrocrack emergence, is noticed.

Generally, from these figures, it can be seen that as the load increases, there is an significant increase of strain concentration near the hole area; but the fringe pattern elsewhere is still uniform and smooth. At higher load level, the fringe patterns in the figures become quite dense; however, the fringe contrast is still excellent, a credit to the moiré interferometry method. Also along the principal material direction of the specimens, i.e., $0, 45$ and 90 degrees to vertical axis, a noticeable band where the fringe pattern, and hence the deformation, is different from else where, can be observed. These bands are attributed to very large strains as compared to other regions. The shapes of the patterns also elucidate shear deformation as compared to the normal one plays more important role in damage characteristics of unidirectional composite laminate.

It should be pointed out that all the fringe patterns shown, include some initial fringes, partly due to the imperfections in the optics and partly due to the small clamping load that has to be applied to the specimen. This pattern has to be subtracted from the subsequent patterns to obtain deformation information due to the external load exclusively. Furthermore, another usefulness of the carrier pattern, which can be formed by changing the angle α of the two incident light beam, is that it can be added initially to increase the density of fringes when the original pattern is sparse because of small deformation, or reduce the density of fringes as the original pattern is too dense due to large deformation of the specimen. This procedure is important to aid the latter image processing in the calculation of displacement and strain of the specimen.

Quantitative evaluation of the moiré patterns taken from the experiment, even with computer processing, is very tedious and time consuming considering that the pictures shown in Figures 3-5 are only a few samples of the many that were recorded at regular intervals. For simplicity, in what follows, one strain component ϵ_{yy} distribution along the horizontal x axis is taken into account. Similar procedure can be applied to obtain other strain components. The developed image processing software based on the technique described in section 3 has been employed to evaluate the deformation field of the specimen under a certain load level. For comparison, the strain distribution prediction result is generated by using finite element method with linear elasticity theory. The whole specimen is modeled by 96 two-dimensional 8-node isoparametric elements. The half element layout is illustrated in Figure 1. The material parameters as input data are $E_{11}=1.25 \times 10^5$ MPa, $E_{22}=1.11 \times 10^4$ MPa, $\nu_{12}=0.338$, $G_{12}=3.3 \times 10^3$ MPa.

In Figure 6, the comparison result of the strain component in y direction ϵ_{yy} variation along the horizontal x axis is illustrated for the 90° specimen under the load of 440N. It can be seen that there exists difference between the prediction and experimental results. It has been found that the difference of strain magnitude will be more evident as the applied load increases. This is attributed to the inelastic behavior of the specimen due to material damage.

5. Summary

The behavior of notched unidirectional composite laminates can be analyzed both theoretically and experimentally. The moiré interferometry technique, due to its potential for revealing in-plane displacement fields of specimens, has been employed to analyze the response of unidirectional composite laminate containing a central circular hole. Results given from the tests and analyses conducted on unidirectional graphite fiber epoxy composite laminates under off-axis tension illustrate the fundamental deformation behavior due to a hole. Although the notch form which the attention is mainly paid to is circular hole, other kinds notches such as cracks, elliptical holes etc. or multiple notches can also be analyzed without increasing complication. The image processing system making use of fast Fourier transform technique eliminates the laborious and subjective procedures encountered in conventional moiré method and enables automatic and quantitative strain analysis to be performed for the fringe patterns obtained from the experiments. Comparison between the experimental and theoretical results manifests that nonlinear analysis taking material damage into account may provide better behavior estimation for composite materials.

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Reference

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Figure 1. Unidirectional laminate with a hole subjected to tension.

Figure 2. Optical arrangement for moiré interferometry.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3. Fringe patterns for 0° specimen.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4. Fringe patterns for 45° specimen.

Figure 5. Fringe patterns for 90° specimen.

Figure 6. Strain ϵ_{yy} distribution along x-axis for 90° specimen.